

Original Research

The Impact of Multiple Directorships on Shareholder Value Creation: Baseline Evidence From South Africa

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Abstract

This study aimed to investigate the impact of multiple directorships (MDs) on shareholder value creation (SVC) for 101 non-financial companies listed in South Africa from 2013 to 2022. A quantitative quasi-experimental approach was employed to evaluate the hypotheses. Data sources included integrated annual reports, OSIRIS and Who Owns Who databases. The measures of MDs comprised the proportion of independent non-executive directors with multiple directorships (PINED_MD), dummy variables for this proportion (D_PINED_MD), and the average number of board seats held by INEDs (AVEBST_INED). SVC was measured using standard market value added (SMVA), market-to-book ratio (MTB) and Tobin's Q (TBQ). Fixed effects models (FEM) were used to test the hypotheses. The curvilinear quadratic FEM revealed that PINED_MD exhibited an inverted U-shaped effect on SMVA and MTB, attaining maximum value when PINED_MD was between 80% and 100%. In comparison, a U-shaped effect on TBQ reached a minimum turning point when PINED ranged between 20% and 40% of the INEDs. AVEBST_INED displayed an inverted U-shaped effect on all SVC measures that attained optimal values when AVEBST_INED was 12. The statistical results suggested that MDs can enhance or diminish shareholder value, consistent with the integration of reputation and busyness hypotheses. The study highlighted the necessity of imposing limits on MDs.

Keywords: Corporate Governance, Curvilinear Quadratic Models, Independent Non-Executive Directors, Multiple Directorships, Shareholder Value Creation, South Africa.

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Introduction

The board of directors is a fundamental component of the internal corporate governance framework and oversees the integrity of the firm's financial statements (Alhaddad et al., 2022). Boards are crucial in shaping the strategic direction and monitoring organisational performance (Fayad et al., 2024). The main goal of a board is to safeguard shareholders' interests, ultimately increasing the company's value and enhancing shareholder wealth (PeiZhi & Ramzan, 2020). One of the critical issues impacting the effectiveness of the board's monitoring and advisory roles is the phenomenon of multiple directorships (MDs) (Kim, 2022). MDs, often referred to as director busyness, describe board members who hold three or more outside directorships (Alqahtani et al., 2022; Bazrafshan & Hesarzadeh, 2022). MDs are a unique feature of the independent non-executive directors (INEDs) market (Lin & Brown, 2022). The issue of MDs on corporate boards has come under increasing scrutiny from investors and regulators (Lee & Lok, 2020). For instance, Hong Kong has attempted to limit the number of INED positions they could hold. However, it received strong market opposition during the consultation period (Liu & Liu, 2023). On the other hand, Spain has no legal limitation to the number of boards a director can serve (Aguiar-Díaz et al., 2024). However, Spain's good governance codes have urged companies to establish rules on the number of boards on which their directors can sit. Thus, Spain modified board regulations between 2015 and 2020 by setting out the maximum number of boards a director could sit on (Aguiar-Díaz et al., 2024). However, the South Africa Companies Act 71 of 2008 does not restrict the number of board seats INEDs may occupy, which may affect the effective exercising of their fiduciary duties.

Whether MDs on corporate boards benefit or harm shareholder value remains debatable (Le et al., 2023). Current evidence is mixed, and the impact of MDs on shareholder value creation (SVC) is a contentious issue among scholars (Kim, 2022). Thus, extensive discussions have taken place regarding the implications of MDs, yielding varied conclusions (Trinugroho et al., 2023). There are two competing hypotheses on the issue. First, the reputation hypothesis suggests that directors on multiple boards possess enhanced reputational skills, potentially leading to conflicting outcomes (Latif et al., 2024). Advocates of this view argue that such overlaps provide directors with improved access to crucial resources, strategic information, and increased legitimacy (Limbasiya & Shukla, 2019).

Conversely, the busyness hypothesis asserts that the extensive responsibilities of these directors may overwhelm their schedules, hindering their capacity to fulfil shareholder obligations effectively (Gray & Nowland, 2018; Shin & Park, 2023). Criticism grows particularly when a director holds three or more board positions, which can lead to excessive commitments and a consequent decline in attention devoted to each role (Chee & Tham, 2021). Multiple board positions may restrict a director's ability to dedicate sufficient time and focus, adversely affecting their commitment, accountability, and overall effectiveness (Saleh et al., 2020; Lin & Brown, 2022). Thus, the accumulation of directorships is a complex issue that presents both positive and negative aspects (Chou & Feng, 2019).

Shareholders of listed companies in South Africa and other stakeholders have become increasingly concerned about the prevalence of multiple board directorships held by INEDs (Mokobane, 2023). The South African Companies Act 71 of 2008 does not address the regulation of these MDs, which can adversely impact the effectiveness of INEDs in fulfilling their fiduciary duties. If shareholders do not fully understand the implications of these overlapping roles, they may inadvertently elect or re-elect INEDs who are too distracted to perform their responsibilities effectively. Conversely, shareholders may hesitate to appoint INEDs with multiple board roles without considering their ability to manage these varied responsibilities simultaneously. South Africa's King IV Report on Corporate Governance advises that potential INEDs disclose their other board positions and submit written statements affirming they have sufficient time to fulfil their board responsibilities. Before appointing a director, South African corporate boards or nomination committees must evaluate the number of other directorships held by the candidate in both listed and unlisted companies. They should also assess the director's experience and ability to manage their duties effectively (Institute of Directors in South Africa ((IODSA), 2016). The theoretical complexities surrounding appointing directors to more than one board leave the unresolved empirical question of how MDs influence shareholder value creation (SVC) (Bravo-Urquiza et al., 2024). Considering the conflicting arguments about the effectiveness of directors with MDs, this study aims to examine the impact of MDs on shareholder value creation (SVC) of South African non-financial companies listed on the JSE between 2013 and 2022.

This paper is primarily written to answer the question: Are multiple directorships detrimental to the company's SVC in South Africa? Surprisingly, although this issue has been highlighted many times in South Africa's news or public discussions, the empirical approaches are still minimal. Therefore, this study provides at least four contributions. First, this study sheds light on how MDs affect the quality of managerial oversight and SVC in INEDs. Second, the number of outside board seats in INEDs may signal the directors' reputation. Third, the effects of MDs of INEDs have been extensively analysed in developed countries. Fourth, a significant lack of studies exists in emerging markets like South Africa, where MDs of INEDs raise significant concerns. To consolidate the reputation and busyness hypotheses, this study used linear and curvilinear effects of INEDs holding multiple board roles on SVC.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. The next section presents the literature view followed by research methodology, empirical results and discussions, conclusions, theoretical implications, policy implications, limitations and recommendations for future research.

Literature review

Theoretical literature review

This study uses agency and resource dependency theories to inform the hypotheses and evaluate the results.

Agency theory

Agency theory posits that the board of directors acts as the overseer of management, aiming to mitigate the principal-agent problem that arises between shareholders (the principals) and managers (the agents) (Hammami et al., 2024). This theory suggests that the primary functions of corporate boards include operating independently and identifying and deterring discretionary managerial actions through a robust system of monitoring and control on behalf of investors and other stakeholders in the firm (Hundal, 2017). A central argument presented in this paper is that the level of busyness of boards, characterised by MDs, influences the independence of corporate directors (Kutubi et al., 2021). Having MDs can enhance directors' expertise in monitoring management and prevent wealth-diminishing decisions (Alhaddad et al., 2022). Also, MDs can lead to ineffective oversight if directors lack time to meet their responsibilities across several companies simultaneously (Mans-Kemp et al., 2020). Moreover, MDs may provoke opportunistic behaviour in some directors, raising ethical concerns as they reap the benefits of prestige and fees from board memberships while overextending themselves to the detriment of shareholders (Saleh et al., 2020).

Resource dependency theory

The resource dependency theory conceptualises agents as valuable resources facilitating social and business networks (Latif et al., 2024). According to this theory, directors on corporate boards are crucial for establishing connections that enable access to resources in the form of information, which can be leveraged for the company's benefit (Abd Alhadi et al., 2021). In alignment with the resource dependence theory, independent board members contribute essential resources, such as expertise, knowledge, legitimacy, and social connections, enhancing their effectiveness (Le et al., 2022). Furthermore, the theory posits that directors' diverse backgrounds, skills, and expertise can bolster their reputations, allowing them to fulfil their fiduciary duties with due diligence and responsibility (Le et al., 2023). One implication of the resource dependency perspective on MDs is that each additional board position can introduce new linkages and resources to the board (Jahan et al., 2021). MDs are believed to positively influence identifying and evaluating strategies and alternatives and cultivating relationships within the external environment (Shin & Park, 2023). Thus, the primary role of the board of directors from the resource dependency hypothesis point of view is to act as resource suppliers (Abd Alhadi et al., 2021).

Conceptual literature review

Multiple directorships

Researchers have provided several definitions for MDs (Saleh et al., 2020). For instance, MDs refer to the number of external appointments corporate directors hold (Chee & Tham, 2021; Alhaddad et al., 2022). MDs also refer to the directors serving on three or more boards based on the rule of thumb (Bazrafshan & Hesarzadeh, 2022; Tham, 2024). Many stakeholders have raised concerns over multiple board directorships (Limbasiya & Shukla, 2019). Previous literature indicates that MDs have advantages and disadvantages (Aguilar-Díaz et al., 2024). A review of existing literature indicates that

two primary arguments dominate current discussions on board MDs: the reputation/experience and the busyness hypotheses (Chee & Tham, 2021).

Reputation/experience/ expertise hypothesis

The reputation hypothesis was introduced by Fama and Jensen (1983) within the framework of resource dependency theory. The reputation hypothesis suggests that having MDs signals higher quality and better monitoring capacity of said directors (Lee & Lok, 2020; Shin & Park, 2023). Also, the reputation hypothesis further posits that companies with busy directors are more inclined to distribute profits to shareholders and do so at higher levels, which helps to alleviate agency problems and enhance shareholder returns (Benson et al., 2022). Furthermore, talented and reputable directors are in greater demand, often leading to increased busyness (Kim, 2022).

The resource dependence theory underpins the experience/expertise hypothesis (Bravo-Urquiza & Reguera-Alvarado, 2025). The experience hypothesis asserts that serving on multiple boards provides directors with valuable experience, enhancing their effectiveness in governance (Martins & Costa, 2020). The reputation hypothesis suggests that directors with numerous board positions possess more extraordinary experience, skills, and expertise, contributing to improved monitoring mechanisms (Chee & Tham, 2021). Research indicates multiple appointments can result in a high directorial reputation and quality. Directors holding multiple board positions may acquire new expertise and develop valuable network connections in the external environment, benefiting the firm (Alhaddad et al., 2022). Advocates of the experience hypothesis argue that these directors have better access to information regarding market conditions, competitors, customers, and suppliers, enabling them to provide higher-quality advice to the firm's top management (Chakravarty & Hegde, 2022). Directors with MDs are often regarded more favourably in directorship markets due to their perceived high competence (Alexeyeva, 2023). Furthermore, MDs signal director quality, as capable directors are highly sought after in the labour market (Chen et al., 2015). Thus, to preserve their reputation, these directors impart advice and proper guidance to elevate firms' performance, financial reporting quality and firm value (Alsheikh, 2023; Tham et al., 2025).

Busyness hypothesis

The busyness hypothesis is rooted in agency theory (Alhaddad et al., 2022). On the negative side, directors with multiple board appointments may cause disadvantages for firms based on the busyness hypothesis (Liu & Liu, 2023). The busyness hypothesis posits that serving on multiple boards results in distracted and/or overcommitted directors, which diminishes corporate governance effectiveness (Clements et al., 2015; Tham, 2024). This reduction in oversight may exacerbate agency conflicts, as managers are better positioned to pursue their interests at the expense of shareholders (Lee & Lok, 2020). Moreover, board busyness influences the monitoring and advising functions of the board differently, and the needs for monitoring and advising are not uniform across all firms (Bazrafshan & Hesarzadeh, 2022). Investors increasingly vote against board members who are "too busy"; thus, investor pressure exists to limit the number of board seats that directors may hold in a public company.

The busyness hypothesis posits that serving on multiple boards simultaneously can over-commit an individual to the responsibilities of those boards (Safari, 2022). Time commitments should be the foremost consideration when accepting another directorship, as the demands for effectively fulfilling board duties are increasingly rising (Mans-Kemp et al., 2020). The busyness hypothesis suggests that directors on multiple boards may struggle to monitor and advise management efficiently due to time constraints, scheduling conflicts, and limited efforts (Al-Dubai & Alotaibi, 2023). Many researchers contend that accumulating numerous external directorships is closely linked to inefficient corporate governance, heightened agency costs, and negative impacts on business operations (Le et al., 2023). Simultaneously holding concurrent external positions often hinders independent directors from diligently executing their responsibilities, weakening corporate governance (Moursli, 2020). A director's busyness has different consequences depending on whether the director is an executive or a non-executive (Latif et al., 2024). Consequently, the busyness hypothesis suggests a negative correlation between busy directors and SVC (Benson et al., 2022; Lin & Brown, 2022).

Shareholder value creation

The creation of shareholder value has been a focal point of research for over eighty years and continues to interest investors (Lafont et al., 2021). Increasing shareholder value has become a primary objective for corporate managers (Behera, 2021). This raises important questions about creating and accurately measuring shareholder value effectively. However, the debatable topic is which measures can describe SVC. SVC can be assessed through traditional accounting-based measures and value-based management (VBM) measures (Agrawal et al., 2019).

The primary traditional accounting-based measures for quantifying SVC include earnings per share (EPS), return on equity (ROE), return on assets (ROA), and dividend per share (DPS) (Hall, 2024). One significant advantage of these measures is their straightforward calculation and relatively high comparability among companies across different sectors of the economy. However, it is essential to recognise their limitations as well. Traditional accounting measures rely heavily on historical data to assess a company's short-term performance (Inkpen & Sundaram, 2022). Moreover, these measures are inherently backwards-looking, primarily influenced by accounting conventions, and tend to highlight management's achievements (Singla & Prakash, 2023). They are also susceptible to manipulation, as managers may sometimes engage in earnings management to present a more favourable financial picture when their compensation is tied to such figures (Nieuwoudt & Hall, 2022). Additionally, traditional performance metrics prioritise company performance over shareholder interests (Yaman & Topal, 2024). Criticisms also arise regarding their failure to account for the total cost of capital, time value of money, cash flows, and accrual-based accounting conventions (Sura et al., 2023). Furthermore, they do not provide a clear strategic direction for value management. Consequently, traditional accounting measures have been challenged and increasingly supplemented by VBM measures for assessing SVC (Elgharbawy & Abdel-Kader, 2021).

VBM is a systematic approach to corporate management with the primary objective of maximising shareholder value. VBM is a comprehensive managerial strategy that aligns

corporate actions with value creation (Elgharbawy & Abdel-Kader, 2021). Among the widely recognised VBM measures are market capitalisation (MCAP), Tobin's Q, the market-to-book (MTB) ratio, economic value added (EVA), market value added (MVA), total shareholder returns (TSR), and the price-to-earnings (P/E) ratio (Sura et al., 2023). These VBM measures were developed to address certain limitations by focusing not solely on cash flows and cost of capital but on a firm's actual economic profit, considering the costs of debt and equity capital invested (Arnold et al., 2023). One of the critical principles behind employing VBM measures in corporate management is to minimise the gap between a company's potential and its current market value. Despite the increasing significance of VBM measures, there remains a dearth of academic research exploring their application in assessing SVC. One reason for scholars' limited use of VBM measures is their inherent complexity.

Empirical literature review and hypotheses development

Indeed, MDs have emerged as a global phenomenon within the business landscape, igniting vigorous discussions among regulators, professionals, and academics (Marei et al., 2024; Bravo-Urquiza & Reguera-Alvarado, 2025). The empirical evidence concerning the relationship between MDs and shareholder value creation (SVC) is varied and often contradictory. For instance, Lee and Lok (2020) examined data from 400 firms, comprising 1,730 firm-year observations across Malaysia, the Philippines, Singapore, and Thailand between 2012 and 2016. The study evaluated MDs through the proportion of independent non-executive directors (INEDs) holding MDs (PINED_MD) and developed a dummy variable that equals one when D_PINED_MD is at least 50%. Additionally, they investigated the average number of board seats held by INEDs (AVEBST_INED). Proxies for SVC included return on assets (ROA) and Tobin's Q (TBQ). The results from the fixed effects model (FEM) indicated that all measures of board MDs significantly and negatively influenced both ROA and TBQ, aligning with the agency theory and the busyness hypothesis. Similarly, a study by Latif et al. (2020) focused on 333 listed companies on the Pakistan Stock Exchange from 2006 to 2011. This research employed the same measures of MDs—PINED_MD, D_PINED_MD, and AVEBST_INED—with TBQ as the primary metric for assessing SVC. The findings from both the FEM and the generalised method of moments (GMM) showed that PINED_MD and D_PINED_MD had a significant negative effect on TBQ, while AVEBST_INED demonstrated an insignificant negative impact. These adverse outcomes further reinforce the agency theory busyness hypothesis. The current study aims to complement and extend these findings by assessing SVC using multiple measures of VBM. Furthermore, this study employed linear and curvilinear models to test the hypotheses, further validating the reputation and busyness hypotheses.

In a subsequent study, Saleh et al. (2020) investigated 25 non-financial firms listed on the Palestine Security Exchange (PSE) from 2009 to 2016. This research assessed MDs on corporate boards using various metrics: the average number of board seats held by all directors (AVEBST_AD), the average number of board seats occupied by independent directors (AVEBST_INED), and the average number of board seats held by executive directors (AVEBST_ED). The study employed ROA and return on equity (ROE) to evaluate SVC as proxies. The findings from both the FEM and the random effects model (REM) indicated that all measures of MDs had an insignificant positive impact on ROA

and ROE, which partially supports the reputation hypothesis. Conversely, Chakravarty and Hegde (2022) investigated 13,791 firm-year observations of firms listed on the Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE) from 2006 to 2013. Their study measured MDs using indicators such as PINED_MD, D_PINED_MD, and AVEBST_INED, while market-to-book (MTB) was a proxy for SVC. The Panel Ordinary Least Squares analysis revealed that all MDs' metrics significantly positively impacted MTB, aligning with the reputation hypothesis.

In subsequent research, Liu and Liu (2023) examined 9,346 firm-year observations of Hong Kong-listed companies from 2012 to 2018. The study assessed MDs using the D_PINED_MD metric. ROA, Earnings Before Interest and Taxes (EBIT), TBQ and market-to-book ratio (MTB) were used as proxies for SVC. The findings revealed that D_PINED_MD had a significant positive effect on all measures of SVC, which contradicts the predictions of agency theory.

Similarly, Trinugroho et al. (2023) conducted an extensive study involving 392 firms listed in Indonesia from 2014 to 2020. They evaluated MDs using the D_PINED_MD metric while using ROA and TBQ as proxies to measure SVC. Their regression model results indicated that D_PINED_MD had a significant negative effect on TBQ, although its impact on ROA was statistically insignificant yet positive. These negative results align with the agency theory and busyness hypothesis. In a separate investigation, Venkatesh et al. (2024) examined 1,926 companies listed on both the National Stock Exchange (NSE) and the Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE) from 2011 to 2019. This research used PINED_MD and PINED_MD² to measure MDs, again using TBQ as a proxy for SVC. Their findings, derived from FEM analysis, indicated that PINED_MD positively impacted TBQ significantly, while PINED_MD² demonstrated a significant negative effect, suggesting an inverted U-shaped relationship. These results support the integration of the reputation and busyness hypotheses.

The existing theories and empirical research indicate a possible correlation between MDs and SVC measures. This relationship may present as positive, negative, curvilinear, or may have no effect at all. The hypotheses in this study regarding MDs and SVC are based on the principles of corporate governance theories and existing empirical studies, and they are outlined as follows:

H_{1a}: The PINED_MD has a significant positive, negative or no effect on the SVC of South African-listed non-financial companies.

H_{1b}: The D_PINED_MD greater than or equal to 50% has a significant positive, negative or no effect on the SVC of South African-listed non-financial companies.

H_{1c}: The AVEBST_INED has a significant positive, negative or no effect on the SVC of South African-listed non-financial companies.

H_{2a}: The PINED_MD has U-shaped or inverted U-shaped effects on the SVC of South African-listed non-financial companies.

H_{2b}: The AVEBST_INED has U-shaped or inverted U-shaped effects on the SVC of South African-listed non-financial companies.

Figure 1 shows the research model derived from the hypotheses

Figure 1. Research model

Research Methodology

The study employed a quantitative quasi-experimental method to examine how MDs impact SVC as variables are already present in the integrated annual reports and databases. The research methodology section encompasses sample selection, data collection, variable measurements, and the empirical models' specifications.

Sample selection

The study uses a purposive method. The researcher begins with a search of non-financial companies listed on the JSE from the Who Owns Whom (WOW) database from 2013 to 2022. The criteria exclude:

- i. Non-financial companies with headquarters outside South Africa.
- ii. Non-financial companies without JSE as the primary stock exchange.
- iii. Non-financial companies with missing SVC and INEDs directorship data

Table 1 illustrates the process followed in selecting the final sample size for this study.

Table 1. Sample selection process for hypotheses testing

Sampling criteria	No. of companies
Total number of non-financial companies listed on the JSE in 2013 – 2022	186
Less companies with headquarters outside South Africa	30
South African non-financial companies	156
Less South African non-financial companies with missing data	55
Final sample	101
Company- year observations × 10 years	1010

Theoretically, the sampling using Slovin's formula is as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+Ne^2} = \frac{156}{1+156(0,1)^2} = 60.9 \text{ or } 61 \text{ non-financial companies.}$$

Where:

n is the number of members of the sample; N is the target population and e is the error tolerance limit of 10%. Then, from the data given:

The sample size of 101 companies exceeds the estimated minimum sample size of 61 companies, and it is sufficient to support the generalisation.

The JSE-listed non-financial companies in the sample were categorised using the Industry Classification Benchmark (ICB) into ten industries: Oil & Gas, Basic Materials, Industrials, Consumer Goods, Health Care, Consumer Services, Telecommunications, Utilities, and Technology. Table 2 presents a breakdown of the sample by industry. The most significant representation comes from the Industrials sector, comprising 31.7% of the sample, followed by Consumer Services at 21.8%, Basic Materials at 18.8%, Consumer Goods at 10.9%, Technology at 6.9%, Telecommunications at 5.0%, and Health Care at 5.0%. It is important to note that no companies from the Oil & Gas, and Utilities sectors from this analysis.

Table 2. Sample distribution by industry

ICB code	Industry type (non- financial)	No. of companies	%
J500	Oil & Gas	0	0.0
J510	Basic Materials	19	18.8
J520	Industrials	32	31.7
J530	Consumer Goods	11	10.9
J540	Health Care	5	5.0
J550	Consumer Services	22	21.8
J560	Telecommunications	5	5.0
J570	Utilities	0	0.0
J590	Technology	7	6.9
Total		101	100.0

Data collection sources

This research collected data from three sources: the Osiris database, integrated annual reports, and the WOW database.

OSIRIS database: The OSIRIS database is a comprehensive resource offering detailed global information on companies. The OSIRIS database enhances the value of this data by gathering information from diverse sources, standardising it, and establishing connections between them. The OSIRIS database includes a wide array of information, such as standardised financials, ratings, financial strength indicators, original filings and images, profiles and contact details of current and former directors, stock data, private equity information and portfolios, patents, thorough corporate and ownership structures, industry research, as well as business and company-related news. Consequently, the OSIRIS database provides valuable statistics on shareholder creation data.

Integrated annual report: The publication of integrated annual reports is mandatory for companies listed on the JSE. Due to the rigorous auditing process that annual reports undergo before release, a high degree of validity in the data is generally acknowledged. As a result, the researcher used the corporate governance report to gather profiles of the directors, including their names, designations (EDs, NEDs and INEDs), date of appointment and date of resignation or termination. However, it is worth noting that most integrated annual reports do not provide information on the directorships of INEDs, which is the focus of this study. However, some integrated annual reports still offer valuable information for the study, such as the names of INEDs, their date of appointment, and their date of resignation or termination. Thus, the Who Owns Whom database addresses the issue of directorships as it contains directorships of all listed companies on the JSE which includes the previous and current directorships.

Who Owns Whom (WOW) database: The WOW database was established in 1980 in Cape Town, South Africa, as an independent entity committed to producing thorough and unique research on African companies and industries. The WOW database includes comprehensive industry research papers, detailed company profiles that outline their operations across Africa, corporate ownership structures, and biographies of directors and management. It also offers valuable insights into the continent's mergers and acquisitions and trends in foreign direct investment. This database is a vital research resource, covering nearly 300 significant African sectors. Notably, WOW addresses gaps in directors' biographies by identifying current and past directorships and their appointment and resignation/termination dates. The WOW database's search engine plays a crucial role in gathering information on MDs of INEDs.

To summarise, the independence of the board of directors is a vital characteristic that can significantly influence firm performance (Chatterjee, 2021). Independent directors are considered essential governance mechanisms that monitor management behaviour and minimise agency costs (Reguera-Alvarado & Bravo, 2017). This study focused on INEDs rather than executive directors (EDs) to examine the former's role as effective monitors and advisors in the firm's operations (Shin & Park, 2023). Investigating INEDs aligns with the existing literature on MDs (Ferris et al., 2020). Both scholars and practitioners regard the presence of INEDs in organisations as a fundamental component

of internal governance (Institute of Directors South Africa (IoDSA), 2016). INEDs lack economic and personal connections to the company and its management (van Vuure et al., 2022). Therefore, this focus may overlook the potential impact of MDs held by EDs who represent employees on the board. In this context, the study compiled a dataset of directorships by collecting the names of all INEDs along with their respective companies. The data was organised and the number of directorships held by each director was tallied. For the purposes of this study, MDs are defined as INEDs serving on three or more boards. A partially completed data collection sheet used in this study is presented in Table 3, which includes crucial details such as the company name, financial year-end, names of INEDs, their designations (DESGN), and the dates of their appointments (DA), terminations (DT), and board seats (BST).

Table 3. INEDs board seats data collection sheet

Name of company: e.g., AngloGold Ashanti Ltd								
Financial year ended: 31 Dec				2013	2014	.	2021	2022
Director name	DESGN	DA	DT	BST	BST	.	BST	BST
Sipho Pityana	INED	Feb- 07	Dec- 20	5	5	.		
Rhidwaan Gasant	INED	Aug- 10		2	2	.	1	1
Maria Richter	INED	Jan- 15			1	.	1	1
Nelisiwe Magubane	INED	Apr- 17					9	8
Sindiswa Zilwa	INED	Jan- 20	Oct- 22				1	1

Variable measurements

Dependent variables

In this study, the authors note that no previous research has exclusively employed these VBM measures to assess SVC. The VBM measures utilised in this research include Tobin's Q (TBQ), the market-to-book ratio (MTB), and market value added (MVA). These serve as proxies for SVC and represent the dependent variables. MVA is a tool designed to gauge a firm's capacity to enhance shareholder value (Ichسانی et al., 2024). MVA reflects the value of shares minus the shareholders' capital. A positive MVA indicates that a firm creates value for its shareholders, whereas a negative MVA suggests destroying shareholder wealth (Dobrowolski et al., 2022). The MVA is applicable for assessing a company's performance at a particular time and is used for publicly traded companies (Tamulevičienė & Androniceanu, 2020). Instead of using MVA, this study used standard market value added (SMVA), representing the MVA divided by the initial capital to make it comparable with other ratios. The MTB ratio refers to the market value of equity at the end of the year divided by the book value of equity (Hall, 2024). TBQ is often utilised to illustrate a company's growth prospects and ability to generate long-term value. TBQ is calculated by adding the market value of common and preferred stock and the book value of debt divided by the book value of assets (Oana Pintea et al., 2021). A TBQ ratio exceeding 1.0 signals that the company is likely to outperform the industry average, while a TBQ ratio below 1.0 indicates a potential underperformance compared to the overall industry (De Oliveira & Basso, 2024). Tobin's Q, the numerator, partly

reflects the value investors assign to the company's intangible assets (Singla & Prakash, 2023).

Independent variables

The MDs represented the independent variables. This study assessed the prevalence of MDs using three distinct methods. First, MDs are calculated as the proportion of independent non-executive directors (INEDs) holding MDs (PINED_MD). The PINED_MD is the number of INEDs with MDs divided by the total number of INEDs (Ferris et al., 2020). A director is classified with MDs as an indicator variable, which equals one if the INED serves on three or more boards and zero otherwise (Chen & Guay, 2020). Second, the research employed a dummy variable referred to as D_PINED_MD. This variable is dichotomous, taking the value of one if 50% or more PINEDs hold three or more directorships and zero otherwise (Chee & Tham, 2021). Lastly, the study used the average number of board seats held by INEDs (AVEBST_INED) within a given firm each year (Saleh et al., 2020). The AVEBST_INED refers to the total number of board seats (BST) held by INEDs divided by the number of INEDs (Cooper & Uzun, 2022).

Control variables

The study used four control variables used in prior literature. Firm size (Ln FSIZE) is the natural logarithm of total assets (Bazrafshan & Hesarzadeh, 2022). Firm age (Ln FAGE) is the logarithm natural of the number of years since the incorporation of a firm (Benson et al., 2022). Board size (Ln BSIZE) is the natural logarithm of the number of directors on the board (Benson et al., 2022). Leverage (LEV) is the proportion of the company's debt relative to its total assets (Yasmin & Utama, 2020); Trinugroho et al., 2023).

Empirical regression models for hypotheses testing

This research investigates the effect of MDs on the shareholder value of active South African-listed non-financial companies. Panel data analysis is the most efficient technique for analysis when the data contains both time and cross-section dimensions because it considers the unobservable impacts and constant heterogeneity arising from each company's different attributes (Handa & Mahajan, 2023). The issue of simultaneity necessitates using a fixed effects model panel data technique that can cope with endogeneity's difficulties and the unobservable fixed effects connected to each unit of analysis. This section developed models for this study based on fixed effects panel data econometric models. The study used STATA 18 and Python programming to evaluate the following models.

H1a to H1c: Board multiple directorships and shareholder value creation measures (linear models).

$$SMVA_{i,t}/MTB_{i,t}/TBQ_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PINED_MD_{i,t} + \beta_2 D_PINED_MD_{i,t} + \beta_3 AVEBST_INED_{i,t} + \beta_4 LnFSIZE_{i,t} + \beta_5 LnFAGE_{i,t} + \beta_6 LnBSIZE_{i,t} + \beta_7 LEV_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Where:

SMVA is the standard market value added, MTB is the market-to-book ratio, TBQ is Tobin's Q, PINED_MD is the proportion of INEDs with MDs, D_PINED_MD is computed as a dummy variable that takes the value of 1 if 50% or more of the PINED holds three or more directorships and zero otherwise, AVEBST_INED is the average number of board seats held by an INEDs of a given firm each year, Ln FISIZE is the natural logarithm of firm size, Ln FAGE is the natural logarithm of firm age, Ln BSIZE natural logarithm of board size, LEV is the leverage, β_0 is the constant, $\beta_1 - \beta_3$ are coefficients of independent variables, $\beta_4 - \beta_7$ are coefficients of control variables, i is the company, t is the year and ε is a stochastic error term.

H2a and H2b: Curvilinear quadratic effects of PINED_MD and AVEBST_INED on SVC measures. The curvilinear U-shaped or inverted U-shaped effects are evaluated by adding squared terms. For instance, the impact is a U-shape if $\beta_1 < 0$ and $\beta_2 > 0$ and an inverted U-shape if $\beta_1 > 0$ and $\beta_2 < 0$ (Liang et al., 2022). The curvilinear quadratic models appear as follows:

$$SMVA_{i,t}/MTB_{i,t}/TBQ_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PINED_MD_{i,t} + \beta_2 PINED_MD^2_{i,t} + \beta_3 AVEBST_INED_{i,t} + \beta_4 AVEBST_INED^2_{i,t} + \beta_5 LnFISIZE_{i,t} + \beta_6 LnFAGE_{i,t} + \beta_7 LnBSIZE_{i,t} + \beta_8 LEV_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

SMVA is the standard market value added, MTB is the market-to-book ratio, TBQ is Tobin's Q, PINED_MD is the proportion of INEDs with MDs, PINED_MD² is the proportion of INEDs with MDs squared, AVEBST_INED is the average number of board seats held by an INEDs of a given firm each year, AVEBST_INED² is the average number of board seats held by an INEDs of a given firm each year squared, Ln FISIZE is the natural logarithm of firm size, Ln FAGE is the natural logarithm of firm age, Ln BSIZE natural logarithm of board size, LEV is the leverage, β_0 is the constant, $\beta_1 - \beta_3$ are coefficients of independent variables, $\beta_4 - \beta_7$ are coefficients of control variables, i is the company, t is the year and ε is a stochastic error term.

Empirical results and discussion

Descriptive statistics

Table 4 summarises the research variable statistics from 2013 to 2022. The descriptive statistics include the mean (Mean), standard deviation (SD), minimum (Min), and maximum (Max) of the chosen variables. Table 5 provides descriptive statistics for our sample. The results for dependent variables reveal that SMVA has a mean value of 0.57 with a minimum value of -35.71 and a maximum value of 24.96. MTB has a mean value of 1.39, with a minimum value of 0.00 and a maximum value of 20.62. TBQ is 1.24 with an SD value of 3.69, a minimum value of -41.18 and a maximum value of 63.95.

Regarding independent variables, PINED_MD has a mean value of 0.6, with a minimum of 0.00 and a maximum of 1.00. D_PINED_MD shows a mean value of 0.73, with the same minimum and maximum range. Most INEDs of the South African-listed non-financial companies on the JSE serve on more than three directorships. AVEBST_INED has a mean value of 4.51, with a minimum of 0.00 and a maximum of 13.2. A study conducted by Lee and Lok (2020) on 400 firms, encompassing 1,730 firm-

year observations across Malaysia, the Philippines, Singapore, and Thailand from 2012 to 2016, reported that AVEBST_INED had a mean value of 2.83, which is lower than 4.51. Similarly, PINED_MD recorded a mean value of 0.52, less than 0.6, and D_PINED_MD had a mean of 0.56, lower than 0.73. Conversely, research by Latif et al. (2020) involving 333 companies listed on the Pakistan Stock Exchange from 2006 to 2011 found that AVEBST_INED had a mean value of 2.14, less than 4.51. In this study, PINED_MD exhibited a mean of 0.28, falling short of 0.73, while D_PINED_MD showed a mean of 0.26, again under 0.73.

About control variables, Ln FSIZE has an average value of 15.57, with a minimum of 8.87 and a maximum of 19.98. Meanwhile, Ln FAGE has an average value of 3.79 (equivalent to 54.88 years), a minimum value of 2.30 (10 years), and a maximum value of 4.91 (136 years). BSIZE had an average value of 10.96, with a minimum of 4.00 and a maximum of 22.00. LEV has an average value of 0.78, with a minimum of 0.00 and a maximum of 40.49.

Table 4. Sample descriptive statistics

Variables	Obs	Mean	SD	Min	Max
Dependent variables					
SMVA	1010	0.57	2.89	-35.71	24.96
MTB	1010	1.39	2.20	0	20.62
TBQ	1010	1.24	3.69	-41.18	63.95
Independent variables					
PINED_MD	1010	0.60	0.27	0	1
D_PINED_MD	1010	0.73	0.44	0	1
AVEBST_INED	1010	4.51	2.14	0	13.2
Control variables					
Ln FSIZE	1010	15.57	1.88	8.86	19.98
FAGE	1010	55.46	32.63	10	136
Ln FAGE (in years)	1010	3.79	0.71	2.30	4.91
BSIZE (number)	1010	11.16	3.58	1	22
Ln BSIZE	1010	2,36	0.35	0	3,09
LEV	1010	0,78	2.85	0	40,49

Panel data regression results

Hypotheses H1a to H1c predict that PINED_MD, D_PINED_MD and AVEBST have a significant positive, negative or no effect on SVC measures of South African listed non-financial companies. Table 5 shows the fixed effects model regression results. The results of fixed effects linear regression show that PINED_MD has an insignificant (n.s) negative impact on SMVA ($\beta = -0.788, p = n.s$) and MTB ($\beta = -0.721, p = n.s$), while a significant positive impact on TBQ ($\beta = 2.158, p < 0.1$). D_PINED has an insignificant positive effect on SMVA ($\beta = 0.260, p = n.s$) and MTB ($\beta = 0.308, p = n.s$), while the insignificant negative impact on TBQ ($\beta = -0.874, p = n.s$). The results revealed that PINED had a favourable influence on TBQ compared to SMVA and MTB. On the other

hand, AVEBST_INED had a significant positive impact on SMVA ($\beta = 0.267$, $p < 0.01$) and MTB ($\beta = 0.256$, $p < 0.01$), while the insignificant positive impact on TBQ ($\beta = 0.127$), $p = n.s$). The results highlighted that AVEBST_INED positively influenced SMVA and MTB but did not contribute to TBQ.

Regarding the control variables, Ln FSIZE has a significant negative impact on SMV, p less than 0.01) and MTB (β equals minus 0.844 ($\beta = -0.844$, $p < 0.01$). In contrast, there is an insignificant negative influence on TBQ ($\beta = 8$, $p = n.s$). Ln FAGE has a significant negative impact on all shareholder value-creation measures- SMVA ($\beta = -6.130$, $p < 0.01$), MTB ($\beta = -5.725$, $p < 0.01$) and TBQ ($\beta = -3.812$, $p < 0.01$). Ln BSIZE has an insignificant positive impact on all SVC measures- SMVA ($\beta = 0.661$, $p = n.s$), MTB ($\beta = 0.0930$, $p = n.s$) and TBQ ($\beta = 1.002$, $p = n.s$). LEV has a significant negative impact on all SVC measures- SMVA ($\beta = -0.101$, $p < 0.1$), MTB ($\beta = -0.102$, $p < 0.05$) and TBQ ($\beta = -0.331$, $p < 0.01$).

The analysis of board multiple directorship measures and control variables leads to a conclusion based on comparing R-squared values. Model 2 for MTB demonstrates the highest R-squared at 24.1%, followed by model 1 for SMVA with an R-squared of 15.1%, and then model 3 for TBQ with an R-squared of 4.1%.

Table 5. Multiple directorships and shareholder value creation measures (linear model)

Variables	(1) SMVA	(2) MTB	(3) TBQ
PINED_MD	-0.788 (0.784)	-0.721 (0.542)	2.158* (1.225)
D PINED MD	0.260 (0.367)	0.308 (0.253)	-0.874 (0.573)
AVEBST_INED	0.267*** (0.0910)	0.256*** (0.0629)	0.127 (0.142)
Ln FSIZE	-1.017*** (0.192)	-0.844*** (0.133)	-0.238 (0.300)
Ln FAGE	-6.130*** (0.717)	-5.725*** (0.495)	-3.812*** (1.120)
Ln BSIZE	0.661 (0.535)	0.0930 (0.370)	1.002 (0.837)
LEV	-0.101* (0.0571)	-0.102** (0.0395)	-0.331*** (0.0893)
Constant	37.23*** (3.320)	35.13*** (2.294)	16.05*** (5.188)
Observations	1,010	1,010	1,010
R-squared	0.152	0.241	0.041
No. of companies	101	101	101

Standard errors in parentheses
 *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Hypotheses H2a and H2b propose that PINED_MD and AVEBST_INED exhibit either U-shaped or inverted U-shaped effects on the SVC measures of South African-listed non-financial companies. As illustrated in Table 6, the FEM regression results revealed that PINED_MD had a positive impact on SMVA, while PINED_MD2 negatively influenced SMVA, indicating an inverted U-shaped effect. Furthermore, both PINED_MD and PINED_MD2 revealed detrimental effects on MTB, further supporting an inverted U-shaped effect. In contrast, AVEBST_INED and AVEBST_INED2 positively affect SMVA and MTB, reflecting an inverted U-shaped effect. However, while AVEBST_INED negatively influenced TBQ, AVEBST_INED2 positively influenced TBQ, suggesting a U-shaped effect. The inverted U-shaped findings are consistent with integrating the reputation and busyness hypotheses.

Table 6. Multiple directorships and shareholder value creation (curvilinear quadratic models)

	(1)	(2)	(3)
VARIABLES	SMVA	MTB	TBQ
PINED_MD	0.414	-0.148	-6.914**
	(1.809)	(1.251)	(2.811)
PINED_MD ²	-0.704	-0.121	7.613***
	(1.507)	(1.042)	(2.341)
AVEBST_INED	0.145	0.213	0.188
	(0.274)	(0.190)	(0.426)
AVEBST_INED ²	0.00961	0.00300	-0.00437
	(0.0214)	(0.0148)	(0.0332)
Ln FSIZE	-1.016***	-0.844***	-0.227
	(0.192)	(0.133)	(0.299)
Ln FAGE	-6.140***	-5.755***	-3.909***
	(0.717)	(0.496)	(1.114)
Ln BSIZE	0.662	0.107	1.493*
	(0.547)	(0.378)	(0.849)
LEV	-0.101*	-0.101**	-0.321***
	(0.0572)	(0.0395)	(0.0889)
Constant	37.32***	35.27***	16.44***
	(3.322)	(2.296)	(5.161)
Observations	1,010	1,010	1,010
R-squared	0.152	0.240	0.052
No of companies	101	101	101

Standard errors in parentheses
 *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Graphical analysis of curvilinear quadratic models

The graph illustrated in Figure 2 highlights the curvilinear impact of PINED_MD on SVC measures. It revealed that INED_MD exerts an inverted U-shaped effect on SMVA and MTB, with these measures reaching their optimal values when PINED_MD comprised 80 to 100% of the total INEDs. The number of directorships that generate the

highest shareholder value is denoted as the optimal number of directorships (Lin & Brown, 2022). PINED_MD demonstrated a U-shaped effect on TBQ, with TBQ hitting an optimal when PINED_MD constituted 20 to 40% of INEDs. Beyond this threshold, an increase in PINED_MD correlated with an increase in TBQ. U-shaped or inverted U-shaped relationships suggested that companies should maintain a moderate level of PINED_MD, avoiding excessive INEDs, to maximise shareholder value.

Figure 2. The PINED_MD curvilinear effects on shareholder value creation measures

The graphical representation in Figure 3 illustrates the curvilinear effects of AVEBST_INED on various measures of SVC. The graph indicated that AVEBST_INED exerts an inverted U-shaped influence on SMVA, MTB, and TBQ. SMVA and MTB achieved optimal performance when AVEBST_INED had approximately 12 board seats. Beyond this point, further increases in AVEBST_INED had little effect on SMVA. However, MTB continued to show a modest increase. In contrast, TBQ exhibited a steady upward trend, while AVEBST_INED rose. Consequently, the optimal number of board directorships that maximised shareholder value is around 12 for SMVA and MTB, while TBQ did not define a specific range for directorships. Overall, the results suggested that limiting the number of directorships held by a single INED is advisable to enhance corporate governance practices.

Figure 3. AVEBST_INED curvilinear effects on shareholder value creation measures

Table 7 provides a concise overview of the assessed hypotheses (H). The table presents the H, MD measures, expected signs, actual signs of independent variables, significance (sig) categorised as yes or no, and SVC measures.

Table 7. Summary of hypotheses tested

			Shareholder value creation measures					
H	MD measures	Expected sign	SMVA		MTB		TBQ	
			Sign	Sig	Sign	Sig	Sign	Sig.
H1a	PINED_MD	±	-	No	-	No	+	Yes
Hb	D_PINED_MD	±	+	No	+	No	-	No
H1c	AVEBST_INED	±	+	Yes	+	Yes	+	No
H2a	PINED_MD	±	+	No	-	No	-	Yes
	PINED_MD ²	±	-	No	-	No	+	Yes
H2b	AVEBST_INED	±	+	No	+	No	+	No
	AVEBST_INED ²	±	+	No	+	No	-	No

Discussion of panel data regression results

The study examined the impact of MDs on SVC. Hypotheses H1a to H1c propose that PINED_MD, D_INED_MD, and AVEBST_INED may exert significant positive, negative, or no effects on the SVC of non-financial companies listed in South Africa. The results derived from linear regression models revealed that PINED_MD negatively affected SMVA and MTB while positively influencing TBQ. D_INED demonstrated a positive effect on SMVA and MTB and a negative influence on TBQ. In contrast, AVEBST_INED positively impacted all measures of SVC. These results complemented and expanded upon the research by Lee and Lok (2020), which analysed 400 firms across 1,730 firm-year observations in Malaysia, the Philippines, Singapore, and Thailand between 2012 and 2016. Their study found that PINED_MD, D_INED_MD, and

AVEBST_INED significantly negatively affected ROA and TBQ. Similarly, Liu and Liu (2023) evaluated 9,346 firm-year observations of companies listed in Hong Kong from 2012 to 2018, discovering that D_PINED_MD positively influenced ROA, EBIT, TBQ, and MTB. In contrast, a study by Trinugroho et al. (2023) involving 392 firms listed in Indonesia from 2014 to 2020 indicated that D_PINED_MD had a significantly negative impact on TBQ, while its effect on ROA was not substantial but relatively positive. Furthermore, Chakravarty and Hegde (2022) examined 13,791 firm-year observations from companies listed on the Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE) between 2006 and 2013 and concluded that PINED_MD, D_PINED_MD, and AVEBST_AD positively and significantly influenced MTB. Previous literature research has demonstrated the influence of accumulating board seats on firm performance and corporate governance (Piñeiro-Chousa et al., 2025).

Regarding the curvilinear quadratic models, H2a posits that PINED_MD produces either U-shaped or inverted U-shaped effects on the SVC measures of South African-listed non-financial companies. The curvilinear regression results indicated that PINED_MD positively affects SMVA, whereas PINED_MD2 negatively influences SMVA. Additionally, both PINED_MD and PINED_MD2 negatively influenced MTB. Conversely, PINED_MD positively affected TBQ, while PINED_MD2 negatively impacted TBQ. These results suggested that PINED highlighted either a U-shaped or inverted U-shaped effect on SVC measures. Similarly, Venkatesh et al. (2024) examined 1,926 firms listed on the NSE and BSE from 2011 to 2019. While PINED_MD had a significant positive effect on TBQ, PINED_MD2 demonstrated a considerable adverse effect, illustrating inverted U-shaped relationships. These positive and negative outcomes aligned with integrating reputation and busyness hypotheses.

Furthermore, H2b posits that AVEBST_MD exhibits either U-shaped or inverted U-shaped effects on the SVC measures of South African-listed non-financial companies. The results indicated that AVEBST_INED and AVEBST_INED2 positively impacted both SMVA and MTB. In contrast, AVEBST_INED had a negative influence on TBQ, while AVEBST_INED2 demonstrated a positive effect on TBQ. The results from the graphical analysis highlighted that AVEBST_MD exhibited an inverted U-shaped relationship across all SVC measures, which supports the reputation and busyness hypotheses (Tham, 2024). Additionally, a study by Cheung and Lai (2022) involving 1,582 observations from 391 firms listed in the US S&P 500 index, collected between 2015 and 2021, revealed that the average number of directorships held by board members had a U-shaped effect on SVC.

Conclusions

The study investigated the impact of MDs on SVC in South African-listed non-financial companies from 2013 to 2022 using FEM. Data was collected from 101 South African listed non-financial companies over the 10 years, yielding 1,010 company-year observations. MDs were assessed using the PINED_MD, D_PINED_MD and AVEBST_INED. The study employed measured SVC using SMVA, MTB, and TBQ. The linear regression findings revealed that board MDs influence SVC differently, exhibiting positive, negative, or neutral effects. Conversely, the curvilinear regression analysis demonstrated that PINED_MD and AVEBST_INED positively and negatively

affect SVC, reflecting U-shaped or inverted U-shaped relationships. Graphically, SMVA and MTB peaked when the PINED_MD and AVEBST_INED reached 12 board seats, while TBQ displayed a moderate increase beyond this threshold. The results indicated that INED_MDs were prominent within South Africa. The results suggested that tighter restrictions on the number of concurrent directorships should be established to enable INEDs to fulfil their board responsibilities effectively. Nonetheless, the mix of positive and negative outcomes aligns with both the reputation and busyness hypotheses. Therefore, for companies with varying monitoring and advisory requirements, stakeholders may need to weigh the costs and benefits associated with MDs. These findings support previous research, indicating that there is no one-size-fits-all approach to the impact of MDs on SVC measures.

Theoretical implications

The results of this study have several significant theoretical implications. Firstly, they contribute to the ongoing discourse regarding MDs and SVC. The mixed outcomes align with both resource dependency and agency theories concerning MDs. Resource dependency theory suggests that directors with diverse backgrounds, skills, and expertise can enhance their reputations by diligently fulfilling their fiduciary duties (Tham, 2024). In contrast, agency theory indicates that MDs may present certain risks, as some directors might engage in opportunistic behaviours that could be considered unethical. Additionally, INEDs with MDs might exploit the prestige and financial incentives linked to board memberships, potentially leading to overcommitment that can compromise shareholder interests (Alhaddad et al., 2022). This study highlighted two key perspectives: the “busyness” hypothesis and the reputation hypothesis. Proponents of the busyness hypothesis argue that directors with excessive commitments may find it challenging to adequately fulfil their fiduciary responsibilities due to their overwhelming workloads (Gray & Nowland, 2018). This hypothesis emphasises the detrimental effects of being overboarded (Mans-Kemp et al., 2020). Conversely, advocates of the reputation hypothesis assert that directors serving on multiple boards can share their experiences and insights, ultimately benefiting their organisations (Saleh et al., 2020).

Policy implications

The results offer valuable insights for practitioners, including financial analysts and potential investors, who seek to predict the impact of MDs of INEDs on SVC. Additionally, these results can potentially enhance regulatory frameworks in various countries that restrict the number of directorships held INEDs. Furthermore, the results support the regulation of MDs concerning INEDs in emerging markets. Policymakers are encouraged to consider limiting the number of INEDs who also hold MD roles, given the implications this may have for their attendance and participation on boards and the overall effectiveness of these boards. Consequently, stricter limitations could be established regarding the directorships of INEDs to ensure they can fully fulfil their board responsibilities. The empirical evidence presented here can aid policymakers in refining current policies or developing new ones to ensure that INEDs with MDs can effectively perform their duties. Also, this study provides essential insights for shareholders considering appointing directors with MDs.

Limitations and recommendations for future research

The study identifies several limitations that could pave the way for new and intriguing future research avenues. The sample size was confined to data from 156 South African listed non-financial companies on the JSE, with only 64.7% included due to missing data. This research is limited to a single country, indicating that future studies could examine the impact of MDs on SVC through comparative analyses between emerging and advanced economies. Additionally, further research could explore how MDs interact with other demographic attributes of the board, including gender, race, nationality, education level, age, and tenure. Given that the sample spans various sectors, it would be beneficial for future studies to investigate how INEDs with MDs affect SVC within specific industries. Moreover, our current understanding of INEDs' contributions to strategic decision-making processes is limited, underscoring the necessity for research focused on this underexplored aspect of MDs. Such studies may require methodologies that capture internal team dynamics, such as case studies. Lastly, while this research used linear and curvilinear quadratic regression models, future studies should consider the potential of cubic regression models. This concept has not yet been explored in the field of corporate governance.

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